

• • Role of Traditional Tibetan Practices in Contemporary Pedagogy at Central Institute of Higher Tibetan Studies: An Ethnographic Study

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Abstract

The present study focused on exploring the role of traditional Tibetan practices in enhancing contemporary pedagogical issues at the Central Institute of Higher Tibetan Studies, Sarnath, India. The study aimed to explore how the Institute integrates the current pedagogical framework while honouring Traditional Tibetan cultural heritage and to investigate the challenges faced by the Institution while keeping a balance of preserving, transmitting, and integrating Tibetan spiritual, socio-cultural, and moral values with today's recent pedagogical methods in advanced higher studies. As such, the study involved 23 participants in the convenience sample including students, teachers, and administrators of the Institute. Data were collected using an ethnographic approach involving document analysis, a two-week participatory observation, and informal interviews. The study revealed that by incorporating elements from the philosophy of Tibetan Buddhism, meditative practices, and Traditional modes of learning like Riglam—a method of logical reasoning—the Institute successfully creates a well-rounded education for its students. In modern higher education, this Institute has a special place among many other establishments when it comes to preserving and transmitting spiritual traditions, cultural values, and norms inherited from Tibetans. As one of the leading institutions in advanced studies, its mission is to keep Tibet's intellectual and religious heritage intact with integrity while striving for globalisation. **Keywords:** ethnographic study, CIHTS, Tibetan traditions, riglam pedagogy, sowarigpa.

Introduction

The Central Institute of Higher Tibetan Studies (CIHTS) located in Varanasi, India is a renowned educational establishment that focuses on exploring and protecting the culture of Tibet and Buddhist philosophy (CIHTS, 2024). It was established in 1967 by the Government of India at the request of His Holiness the 14th Dalai Lama. It is an epicenter for the displaced Tibetan society and other scholars across the globe, making efforts to link ancient Tibetan wisdom with contemporary teaching-learning practices (Zhang et al., 2008). This traditional wisdom possesses diverse religious, philosophical, and cultural practices that have developed over time (CHITS Institutional, 2024). These rituals are deeply rooted in Buddhism, encompassing various forms of meditation, prayers, and learning deeds with the aim of enhancing personal development (Chen, 2015). In educational terms, these activities perhaps have much to do with cultivating holistic development among students while at the same time instilling reverence for cultural heritage.

Preserving cultural heritage in education is not simply about recalling the past, but allows for the continued existence and transformation of cultural identities (Adam, 2015). In our fast-globalizing world where there is lots of effort toward cultural homogenization, it becomes necessary to incorporate traditional practices in modern pedagogy to safeguard the diversity of human heritage (Kahn, 2011). This ensures that generations after are tied to their ancestral roots.

The main goal of this ethnographic study was to investigate how Tibetan spiritual and cultural practices have been woven into the contemporary pedagogical framework at CIHTS. Another objective of this research was to provide insight into how such practices have been adapted for the modern educational system and influenced teaching methods and student experiences.

There was more than one reason why this investigation matters. By extension, it supports a discourse on culture preservation through schooling, and adds to existing research on the incorporation of indigenous knowledge systems into the academies; besides, these findings are applicable to the institutions that are interested in retaining cultural heritages within their curricula. Additionally, it examined the logical relationship between tradition and innovation thereby giving a new understanding of how Traditional practices can enhance present-day education. CIHTS has been able to incorporate customary Tibetan practices into its methods of teaching and learning. In line with the stated objectives, the study addressed four research questions.

Research Questions

1. How does the CIHTS preserve Tibetan culture and traditions in its educational climate?
2. What are the traditional pedagogical practices involved in teaching learning at CIHTS and how do these teaching methods coincide with modern pedagogy?
3. How do these exercises affect students and teachers in terms of academic and personal development?
4. What are the challenges that come with this transition?

Literature Review

Existing literature on traditional Tibetan practice's effect on modern education provided a basis for this study. Research has shown that preserving traditional customs helped to maintain their identity and sense of belonging, given the case of Tibetans in the diaspora (Giles & Dorjee, 2005; Sun et al., 2021). This role has fallen under the responsibility of educational establishments while Tibetans are resettling in new places and trying to integrate with other people.

Sharapan (2016) examined how Tibetan communities in Nepal negotiated their cultural identity through the preservation of traditional practices amidst a changing social, political, and economic environment. For Tibetans to retain their distinctive character in a foreign land, intentional attempts to preserve cultural traditions such as religion, language, and art forms have been vital.

Moreover, the Indigenous knowledge system has been emphasized by the literature on its integration into mainstream education. United Nations (2019, April 22) advocated that "traditional knowledge is at the core of Indigenous identity, culture, languages, heritage, and livelihoods, and its transmission from one generation to the next must be protected, preserved, and encouraged" (para. 1). Further, Anne Nuorgam, chairperson of the Permanent Forum, said that "we need to ensure that our educational practices, languages, environmental conservation, and management are acknowledged and respected globally, not only by Governments but by all peoples." Stories, carvings, paintings, singing, and dancing can significantly transmit cultural traditions from one generation to another. However, worldwide colonization, exploitation, dispossession, and modernisation have been unceasingly mitigating these aspects (paras. 3–4). The researcher, therefore, has seen how this study can be helpful since it underscores the need to maintain traditional Tibetan practices as they are incorporated into CIHTS's contemporary educational landscape.

Methodology

The researcher adopted an ethnographic approach to investigate how the traditional practices of Tibetans have been incorporated into the learning environment of CIHTS. In 1996, Deering recommended ethnography as a naturalistic approach for understanding and describing the cultural patterns from the participants' perspective without influencing the events or interactions that are taking place at the study site. So, this methodology could be informative to capture the contextual nature of this inquiry.

Data collection was carried out in two stages. In the first step, the researcher performed a documentary analysis the purpose of which was to get an accurate and detailed conception of the history and culture of Tibetan spiritual and educational beliefs and practices together with the modern global practice within the CIHTS community.

The second phase was a two-week hang-out session with the participants and stakeholders from 4–16 October 2023. This session aimed to execute an extensive in-field study whereby the researcher physically participated in the Institute's activities as a participant observer to familiarize himself with the Institute's campus and to interact with students, teachers, and administrators. Additionally, gathering deep, native insight into how Tibetan cultural practices have influenced and are rooted in the CIHTS's teaching methods and learning climate.

During this phase, informal interviews and focus group discussions were conducted with 12 students, 7 teachers, and 3 administrators bearing in mind participants' cultural proscriptions and cultural beliefs, as Pelzang and Hutchinson (2018) asserted that it is essential for researchers to show cultural sensitivity and responsiveness when conducting cross-cultural studies. They also argue that researchers must understand these communities' cultural dimensions to develop robust, ethical research. The researcher, therefore, tried to establish trust with the stakeholders and requested to collaborate according to the participants' expertise in creating knowledge for integrating their input into the study.

Findings and Discussion

After the fieldwork, the collected data were examined using the qualitative approach to uncover significant patterns, themes, and insights. The analysis revealed the following findings per the research questions.

Assimilation of Customary Tibetan Ethnicities on the Atmosphere at CIHTS

The findings highlighted that CIHTS devotedly encompasses Tibetan rituals and intellectual heritage into its institutional structure. CIHTS offers courses under the Fine Arts department including Thangka paintings, Kalchakra Mandala art, the Vajrapani sketch of Buddha, and Tibetan Woodcraft. Thangka—a traditional sacred painting of Buddha—is made from special stone colours on a special cloth. Kalchakra Mandala art is considered as the life cycle of an organism, after completing the Mandala it is removed. Vajrapani sketch is associated with Tibetan Tantric Vidya. The Institute has implemented Tibetan cultural activities such as singing and dancing to preserve cultural traditions, besides, developing aesthetic aspects in the students by practicing these artistic activities. Moral codes like the percept 'Not to Take the Life of Anything Living' are strictly followed. The altruist approach of Tibetan philosophy is deeply rooted in the Institute's everyday course of action. The Institute distributes food for starved people and has provided Rickshaws as a livelihood for weaker sections in the local area of Sarnath (Beneficiary, personal communication, October 10, 2023).

Medical education at the CHITS is provided through an age-old Tibetan medical system, Sowa Rigpa—meaning the science of healing—has been officially recognized and practiced by many countries. It was accepted as a medical system in 2010 and notified in Indian gazette notification in 2017. At present, administrative control of this system is under the Ministry of Ayush, Govt. of India ("CIHTS Sowarigpa & Bhot Jyotish," n.d.). One of the Institute's aims is to preserve, restore, transmit, and disseminate Tibetan literature and intellectual heritage. Shantarakshita and Vaghabhatta libraries efficiently perform these tasks with the help of the Translation, Restoration, and Publication Department of the Institute. These libraries are also equipped with advanced ICT and multimedia set-ups, where a rich amount of Bhot literature and intellectual heritage has been stored in xylograph, manuscript, audio-video, and other digital formats. In addition, the complete set of Kangyur and Tengyur gracefully bestowed by His Holiness the 14th Dalai Lama flourishes the Santarakshita library (CHITS: Library, n.d.). The restoration department is involved in preserving and restoring incomplete or lost classical Indian text from available canonical Tibetan literature. This knowledge is also being translated and published into other languages such as Sanskrit, Hindi, and English to transmit and disseminate among the global community.

Including these long-standing practices has significantly influenced the educational methods and atmosphere at the Institute. These traditional rituals have become a part of the journey of the CIHTS which is shaping the path of teaching and learning takes place in significant ways.

Traditional Pedagogical Practices Involved in Teaching Learning at CIHTS and How These Teaching Methods Coincide with Modern Pedagogy

Teaching methods that were in vogue in Nalanda Buddhist Education such as dialectics, debate sessions, class presentations, intra-class debates, tutorial sessions, and *open discussions have been*

effectively implemented into the teaching of science, social science, and teacher education by the Institute. The Buddhist dialectic method was used to teach Buddhist philosophy at Nalanda. With time, an adaptation was made by Tibetans and this adopted style of dialectics named Riglam consists of three basic elements—argumentation, counter-argumentation, and realisation (Baltzersen, 2023). To achieve a deeper understanding of Buddhist philosophy, Tibetans have been using this method in their monasteries for ages. The aims of providing education established by the Basic Education Policy for Tibetans in Exile (2004) are freedom, altruism, upholding the heritage, and innovation. To achieve these goals, the Basic Education Policy incorporated traditional Tibetan and modern subjects simultaneously into the new education system. Pema (n.d.) reported that His Holiness the Dalai Lama stressed using Riglam in teaching modern as well as traditional disciplines and suggested working on publishing specific textbooks for the same. Consequently, some books on Riglam pedagogy have been published for middle to secondary-level classes to teach science, mathematics, and other modern subjects. Pema also acknowledged Riglam as the most effective traditional pedagogy for learning conventional and modern disciplines since it is not only a path of logical thinking but also encompasses “integrated techniques of 21st-century skills including critical thinking, communication, collaboration, problem-solving, and mindfulness with immense benefit to the learner” (para. 1; see Tenzin Pema as cited in Baltzersen, 2023, for more). The Institute practices this pedagogy for teaching-learning and has organized workshops on teaching science through dialectics for other Tibetan school teachers. Some modern pedagogies such as the project method, experiential learning, and collaborative learning strategies have incorporated the elements of traditional debate and discussion methods. Tutorial sessions are lined up with contemporary remedial teaching. These long-established pedagogies have comprised numerous benefits for instance sharp intelligence, concentration, and higher-order thinking skills.

Perception Among Students and Faculty to the Role of These Practices Within Their Academic and Personal Development

Incorporating time-honoured Indo-Tibetan philosophy, customs, and pedagogical practices into CIHTS has created a more holistic and reflective approach to education. Both students and teachers have noticed improvements in focus, emotional control, and a deeper grasp of the connections between knowledge, personal development, and spirituality. Students reported increased memory and concentration by engaging in activities like meditation and chanting. Furthermore, Open discussion, intra-class debate, and class presentation facilitate building a comfortable and engaging learning environment and encourage them to interact with the content on a profound level. Some students admitted that tutorial sessions helped in learning the subjects at their own pace. Almost all participants accepted the significant role of Riglam in their learning of philosophical and modern subjects in addition to their personal development. Using Riglam pedagogy, they feel a joyful experience of learning and understanding every subject with its in-depth knowledge. Consequently, in every incidence of life, they think critically to examine others' views before concluding rather than passively accepting what they hear or what people say. This shift away from lectures towards learning methods has been beneficial. Students and faculty shared a sense of pride and identity by learning Tibetan rituals and customs. In addition, they also emphasized the significance of these traditions in fostering a connection to heritage enhancing their ability to engage with diverse cultures and preparing them for leadership roles both within the Tibetan community and globally. Many participants highlighted how assimilating practices have enabled them to represent their culture proudly instilling a deep respect for their roots and a commitment to preserving them for coming generations. They credited these practices and Buddhist teachings for emotional stability, empathy, self-awareness, and mindfulness within the Institute's community leading to improved well-being and academic success, for all involved.

Challenges That Come with This Transition

The research also identified contextual challenges in integrating the Tibetan way of life at the Institution as below:

Adjusting to the Host Country's Education System by Immigrant Tibetans :

A foremost concern raised by stakeholders during the study was to survive and preserve their cultural heritage in a different educational setting of the host country. Ngodup (1996) also advocated the same issue in the study: exiled Tibetans had to embrace the host countries' education system, which

was strange to them. However, after the autonomous status within the host country's education System, they have brought many changes to the existing education system.

Navigating the Conflict Between Heritage Preservation and Technological Advancement in Education

The second major difficulty was balancing shielding heritage and meeting the needs of a wide-reaching technology-driven educational environment. The Institution had to manage the conflicts between preserving beliefs and adjusting to the standards of an interconnected society.

Coping With the Dilemma Between Traditional and Modern Pedagogy

A further impediment was handling the clash between modernization and the continuance of ancient distinguished learning models within the educational landscape. This demanded thoughtful planning on blending established customs with current academic standards ensuring that the CIHTS' devotion to cultural conservation did not impede its competence to offer a cutting-edge globally applicable education. In this regard, the Riglam has been seen as a hope of bridging the gap between conventional and modern teaching methods (Baltzersen, 2023).

Maintaining the Quality of the Rich Tibetan Language Among the Tibetan Diaspora:

Most young Tibetan exiles must come to India for their education. As most participants believed that these young exiled have become less efficient in the Tibetan language, Baltzersen (2023) also recognized the hurdle of maintaining the quality of the resonant Tibetan language (Bhot). To overcome this obstacle, the objective set by the Basic Education Policy for exiled Tibetans (2004) of implementing an education system which has the conventional Tibetan education system at its centre and the modern education system as its support (Pema, 2019), has been precisely implemented by the CIHTS and continuously striving to achieve it.

Conclusion

This study uncovers the role of traditional Tibetan customs that influence modern teaching methods at the CIHTS. The findings emphasize the Institute's dedication to preserving and incorporating Tibetan cultural traditions into its educational structure creating a well-rounded learning environment that supports intellectual, emotional, and spiritual growth (e.g., Yang & Dunzhu, 2015; Sun et al., 2021).

The research adds to the understanding of how resilient and adaptable Tibetan culture is especially in the face of diaspora and global challenges. It showcases how ancient practices like meditation, chanting, open debates, Riglam-dialectics, sowa-rigpa medical practice, and rituals can be impeccably integrated into modern educational settings offering valuable lessons for other institutes and education systems aiming to bridge cultural gaps and encourage cross-cultural awareness.

As Tibetans grapple with maintaining their heritage amidst swift social, political, and economic shifts (Postiglione et al., 2004), the CIHTS stands out as a beacon of optimism. It exemplifies how traditional customs can flourish and adapt within educational environments. The inclusion of customs has enabled students and staff to represent their heritage nurturing a deep respect for their roots and a commitment to safeguard it for the next generations.

Despite facing obstacles in this effort, the study acknowledges the CIHTS' unwavering dedication to safeguarding and passing on Tibetan cultural heritage. Since global consensus gradually acknowledges the significance of traditional wisdom in handling the intricate challenges of education faced today (Kloos, 2017; Dalai Lama, 2018), the CIHTS model offers an influential illustration to demonstrate how the ancient practices of Tibetan Traditions can be amalgamated into the modern educational framework.

The present study makes available a pivotal description of the role of conventional Tibetan customs in the modern pedagogical structure of the CIHTS. However, the translation of Tibetan text and the effectiveness of Riglam dialectics as a teaching method for modern subjects can be further investigated to acquire a thorough insight into the CIHTS's distinctive attempt at teaching-learning.

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